

PRO-COAST preregistration: pluralistic ignorance for net-zero and locally relevant attitudes

Introduction

Research questions

What is the existence and nature of pluralistic ignorance regarding attitudes to national net-zero and to local issues? Does level of pluralistic ignorance relate to actual attitude levels? How do differences between perceived and actual attitudes relate to other political and social beliefs?

Principles

This is a Bayesian preregistration where we describe planned reporting of parameters rather than hypotheses, with the primary goal of preventing cherry-picking of results. Parameters have been selected because their posteriors are expected to illuminate discussion of the research questions.

There will be no correcting for multiple testing although many parameters are reported. Multiplicity concerns are mitigated under the Bayesian approach by shrinkage provided by principled informative priors. All parameters listed here must be described when reporting on this study. Parameters not listed here must be described as exploratory when listing results.

This preregistration is easiest to understand in combination with the full questionnaire, which can be found signposted where this preregistration was signposted for reviewers.

Utilised response variables

Variables are ordinal unless otherwise stated.

1. National net-zero support (single item, percent, Q10 in external EUBarometer data: <https://europa.eu/eurobarometer/surveys/detail/3472>)
2. Sample net-zero support (single item G1 in standard PRO-COAST questionnaire Wave 2; all further item codes refer to this questionnaire)
3. Perceived national net-zero support (single item G2)
4. Perceived sample net-zero support (single item G3)
5. Sample local issue attitudes (section E items 1 to 4, selected to match section D items 3 and 4)
6. Sample perceived local issue attitudes (section D items 3 and 4)
7. Stakeholder group identity (H1, nominal)
8. Political ideology, option 1, social conservatism – composite of two items (F9 and F16).
9. Political ideology, option 2, left-right ideology scale – single item (F17).
10. Inter-group trust – composite of 4 items (C1-3, C8).
11. Case study identity (nominal)

Parameters of interest: differences

Difference list

The first class of parameter of interest concerns difference scores which in different ways summarise relevant aspects of potential environmental pluralistic ignorance. For Differences 1 to 7 in the below diagram (with Differences 5-7 being differences between differences), we are interested in (1) the difference itself, and (2) the variation in that difference by two random variables, stakeholder group and case study identity.

Difference variable preprocessing and difference calculations

National-level variable: National support for net-zero (Q10) is a single item already calculated on a percentage scale. It is missing for three non-EU countries present in our sample, and Differences 1, 3, and 5 are therefore missing for the relevant case studies.

Stakeholder-group-level variables: Sample net-zero support (G1), and sample local issue attitudes (Section E items) are on 1-to-5 ordinal scales (support or agreement as values 4 and 5), also with “Don't know / Prefer not to say”. For each group, these are set to percentage of all responses which are 4 or 5 on the response scale.

Individual-level-variables: Perceived national net-zero support (G2), Perceived sample net-zero support (G3), and Perceived sample local issue attitudes (section D, multiple items, not for combination), are all single items on a 0-to-10 scale (number of people out of 10 estimated to support or agree), with “Don't know / Prefer not to say”. They are converted to percentages by multiplying by 10, with “Don't know / Prefer not to say” set to missing.

Multiple variables per individual: There are always two section D items (perceived attitudes) per participant, each corresponding to an exactly equivalent section E item. Some items will be excluded because they do not obviously align with a general pro-environmental axis (see Appendix for specific items). Individuals without excluded items have two Difference 6 values, one for each actual-vs-perceived item pair. Therefore, there are also two Difference 7 values for each participant.

Difference calculations are conducted as per the diagram. For group-level values, the same value is used for every participant in a group.

Difference parameter modelling

The posterior parameters for Differences 1 to 5 are obtained from the following model formula (using the `brm()` function from the R package `brms` and default arguments where not otherwise specified):

$$\text{difference} \sim 1 + (1 \mid \text{case_study}) + (1 \mid \text{stakeholder_group})$$

The model formula for Differences 6 and 7 is the same except because it contains two data points for many participants, it includes a random intercept for participant:

$$\text{difference} \sim 1 + (1 \mid \text{case_study}) + (1 \mid \text{stakeholder_group}) + (1 \mid \text{participant})$$

The median of the fixed intercept posterior and associated 95% credible interval are reported to summarise the difference. The probability of direction (the probability the difference is in the observed direction) is reported to summarise evidence for the difference. The median of the random sigma posteriors (for case study and stakeholder group) and associated 95% credible interval (CI) are reported to summarise the variation in difference, with the lower bound of the 95% CI summarising evidence for non-negligible variation.

To confirm appropriate model fit, two diagnostic plots will be examined: residuals vs fitted values (scatterplot), and residuals vs group (boxplot) will be examined. Models will be adjusted as necessary (for example by modelling residual standard deviation as a function of case study if relevant heteroscedasticity is observed).

Difference priors

There are reasons to have different prior beliefs for the different differences – for example, Difference 1 represents pluralistic ignorance, where we have a strong prior based on literature for a large difference, whereas we have no strong prior for Difference 3. However, having different priors for different difference scores would present a complication and challenge to interpretation. We therefore use the same prior for each difference (model intercept): $\text{normal}(M = 0, SD = 36.0775)$. The SD is derived as follows: the researcher has a prior belief based on informal compilation of extensive evidence that support for different environmental policy is distributed roughly normally with 95% of support percentages between 40% and 90%, and that although perceived support may be lower, it has a similar standard deviation. Then, $\sigma_{\text{support}} = (90 - 40) / z(1 - .05 / 2)$; $\sigma_{\text{difference}} = \text{sqrt}(\sigma_{\text{support}}^2 + \sigma_{\text{support}}^2) = 36.0775$ (as the variance of the difference between two normal distributions is the sum of both variances). The priors for the random sigmas are the same (except half-normal), because these are also expectations about differences between percentages in the same expected range.

Parameters of interest: coefficients predicting differences

Models generating parameters of interest

The second class of parameters of interest are from models predicting Differences 1, 2, and 6, each of which can be interpreted as representing a different form of pluralistic ignorance. Models use `brm()` in the same way as before, and for predicting Differences 1 and 2 the formula is:

$$\text{difference} \sim 1 + \text{ideology} + \text{trust} + (1 + \text{ideology} + \text{trust} \mid \mid \text{case_study})$$

The model formula for Difference 6 is the same, except: (1) because it contains two data points for many participants, it includes a random intercept for participant; and (2) it is also intended to examine whether sample levels of agreement predict the difference between perceived and actual support:

$$\text{difference} \sim 1 + \text{ideology} + \text{trust} + \text{sample_attitudes} + (1 + \text{ideology} + \text{trust} + \text{sample_attitudes} \parallel \text{case_study}) + (1 \parallel \text{participant})$$

The reported parameters of interest from each model are the median and 95% CI for all the fixed betas and random sigmas (except for participant, which is not of interest), and the probability of direction for all the fixed betas.

The parameters each have two versions, one where right-wing ideology is operationalised as social conservatism, and one where it is operationalised as a left-right scale. We register a primary interest in social conservatism and treat the left-right scale as an additional check. This is because the left-right scale will be entirely missing in one case study.

To confirm appropriate model fit, the same procedure as described above will be used.

Priors

Fixed beta priors will be normal($M = 0$, $SD = 0.2581$), with the SD derived from Pearson's r distribution across 322 meta-analyses of effect sizes across social psychology (Richard et al., 2003). Random sigma priors will be Student's t ($M = 0.1221$, $\text{scale} = 0.0852$, $\text{df} = 4.1561$), which is the best-fitting Student's t for a dataset containing inter-study variation estimates from 360 meta-analyses of studies reporting Pearson's r from across the field of psychology (van Erp et al., 2017). Calculations describing these derivations in full are at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20181224>.

As a prior sensitivity analysis, we will also report robustness tests where we repeat the analyses with brm() default priors, which are entirely flat for fixed β , and very wide (and thus uninformative) for random σ (Student's t with mean 0, scale 2.5, and df 3).

Data pre-processing and imputation

All variables included in these models will be standardised through z-transform before inclusion.

The variable `sample_attitudes` in the model for Difference 6 is the percentage agreement, exactly as for sample local issue attitudes in the previous analysis (see "Stakeholder-group-level variables" above).

All "Prefer not to say" responses will be set to missing. "Don't know" (left-right ideology only) will be set to the neutral scale point. Both social conservatism items are reverse coded.

Composite variables (trust and social conservatism) will be formed as the mean of z-transformed individual items, thus they will be validly defined unless all items are missing. If trust has a Cronbach's $\alpha < 0.5$, items for which dropping would improve α will be dropped in order of greatest improvement until $\alpha \geq 0.5$, or if that never happens, the single item C1 is used. Social conservatism will not be used if $r < 0.3$. In that case the single item F16 will be used.

For the model predicting Difference 1 (but not for the intercept models establishing what differences are), the missing values for national net-zero support (Q10) will be imputed,

replaced by values generated by careful consideration of what likely values would be. This allows inclusion of all case studies in this analysis. This is valid because there is good data to inform very educated guesses (e.g., knowledge of values in all EU countries, DESNZ tracker data from the UK which asks a very similar question), and because this analysis does not focus on establishing pluralistic ignorance, but rather explaining perceived attitudes corrected for an estimate of what real attitudes are. The imputed values will be as follows: Norway 82%, UK 61%, Montenegro 57%. The relevant model will also be constructed without this imputation (dropping the relevant case studies), and the results presented as supplementary information, with any differences affecting conclusions highlighted in the main text.

Sample determination

Data collection is underway, but researchers have not accessed data at the point of preregistration. The data will be all data collected by the PRO-COAST consortium stakeholder survey Wave 2 up until 13:00 CET 2026-06-01. The anticipated sample size is somewhere between 600 and 900. If the sample is less than 600 at that point, or if any single case-study has produced less than 50 data points, data collection will be extended for exactly 7 days from the original deadline. There are no reasons for excluding data other than any listed above, and in addition, any group with less than three complete-case participants will be dropped entirely from any analysis in which that is the case.

References

- Richard, F. D., Bond Jr, C. F., & Stokes-Zoota, J. J. (2003). One Hundred Years of Social Psychology Quantitatively Described [doi:10.1037/1089-2680.7.4.331]. *Review of General Psychology*, 331-363. <https://doi.org/10.1037/1089-2680.7.4.331>
- van Erp, S., Verhagen, J., Grasman, R. P. P., & Wagenmakers, E.-J. (2017). Estimates of Between-Study Heterogeneity for 705 Meta-Analyses Reported in Psychological Bulletin From 1990–2013. *Journal of Open Psychology Data*. <https://doi.org/10.5334/jopd.33>

Appendix: Section D items.

Each item is named as per its use in Section D asking respondents about perceived attitudes. Each item corresponds to an identical item in Section E which asks about own corresponding attitude.

Items with Usable = No will be excluded from analysis.

CS	Stakeholder group	Item name	Usable	Item
Ireland	Beach visitors and local citizens	D3_ALL_IE	Yes	Using nature-based solutions (e.g., dune restoration, native planting, etc.) is important for dune protection.
Ireland	Beach visitors and local citizens	D4_ALL_IE	Yes	Human behaviour (i.e. driving on dunes, littering) is considered a threat to Streedagh Beach.
Ireland	Members of academia and relevant experts	D3_ALL_IE	Yes	Using nature-based solutions (e.g., dune restoration, native planting, etc.) is important for dune protection.

Ireland	Members of academia and relevant experts	D4_ALL_IE	Yes	Human behaviour (i.e. driving on dunes, littering) is considered a threat to Streedagh Beach.
Norway	Askøy resident	D3_AR_NO	Yes	I am willing to work hard to address important environmental issues.
Norway	Askøy resident	D4_AR_NO	Yes	I feel confident speaking up about environmental issues in public or with officials.
Norway	Leisure fisher	D3_LF_NO	Yes	I am willing to take good care of my fishing equipment, and ensure that it is updated and renewed when needed.
Norway	Leisure fisher	D4_LF_NO	Yes	I am willing to report lost fishing gear via the app.
Norway	Supporter of an environmental group	D3_EG_NO	Yes	I am willing to work hard to address important environmental issues.
Norway	Supporter of an environmental group	D4_EG_NO	Yes	I feel confident speaking up about environmental issues in public or with officials.
Italy	Local community members	D3_LC_IT	Yes	I am willing to participate in regular beach-cleaning activities in my community.
Italy	Local community members	D4_LC_IT	Yes	I actively avoid walking on or trampling dunes to protect them from further damage.
Italy	Members of NGOs	D3_NGO_IT	No	NGOs raise awareness about dune degradation and protection effectively.
Italy	Members of NGOs	D4_NGO_IT	Yes	My organisation would join a joint task force to address dune degradation and plastic pollution in the lagoon.
Italy	Members of the higher education sector	D3_HE_IT	No	Higher education institutions are effectively sharing knowledge about dune degradation and plastic pollution.
Italy	Members of the higher education sector	D4_HE_IT	Yes	The higher education sector is willing to join a joint task force to address issues related to dune degradation and litter management.
Italy	Local government members	D3_LG_IT	Yes	The local government should implement more actions to restore and protect dunes.
Italy	Local government members	D4_LG_IT	Yes	The local government is willing to join a joint task force to address issues related to dune degradation and litter management.

UK	Nature conservation professional	D3_ALL_UK	Yes	I would help the replacement of grey squirrels by red squirrels by reporting sightings of red and grey squirrels in gardens and elsewhere.
UK	Nature conservation professional	D4_ALL_UK	Yes	I would support proposals to kill grey squirrels locally to make it possible to establish red squirrels.
UK	Farmer or forester	D3_ALL_UK	Yes	I would help the replacement of grey squirrels by red squirrels by reporting sightings of red and grey squirrels in gardens and elsewhere.
UK	Farmer or forester	D4_ALL_UK	Yes	I would support proposals to kill grey squirrels locally to make it possible to establish red squirrels.
UK	Hunter or fisher	D3_ALL_UK	Yes	I would help the replacement of grey squirrels by red squirrels by reporting sightings of red and grey squirrels in gardens and elsewhere.
UK	Hunter or fisher	D4_ALL_UK	Yes	I would support proposals to kill grey squirrels locally to make it possible to establish red squirrels.
UK	Local community member	D3_ALL_UK	Yes	I would help the replacement of grey squirrels by red squirrels by reporting sightings of red and grey squirrels in gardens and elsewhere.
UK	Local community member	D4_ALL_UK	Yes	I would support proposals to kill grey squirrels locally to make it possible to establish red squirrels.
Montenegro	NGO	D3_ALL_ME	Yes	The development of cruise tourism in Boka Kotorska should be planned and regulated to ensure sustainability for future generations.
Montenegro	NGO	D3_ALL_ME	Yes	Cruise tourism in Boka Kotorska often leads to overcrowding and negatively affects the quality of life of the local population.
Montenegro	Private sector	D3_ALL_ME	Yes	The development of cruise tourism in Boka Kotorska should be planned and regulated to ensure sustainability for future generations.
Montenegro	Private sector	D3_ALL_ME	Yes	Cruise tourism in Boka Kotorska often leads to overcrowding and negatively affects the quality of life of the local population.

Montenegro	Academia	D3_ALL_ME	Yes	The development of cruise tourism in Boka Kotorska should be planned and regulated to ensure sustainability for future generations.
Montenegro	Academia	D3_ALL_ME	Yes	Cruise tourism in Boka Kotorska often leads to overcrowding and negatively affects the quality of life of the local population.
Montenegro	Public sector	D3_ALL_ME	Yes	The development of cruise tourism in Boka Kotorska should be planned and regulated to ensure sustainability for future generations.
Montenegro	Public sector	D3_ALL_ME	Yes	Cruise tourism in Boka Kotorska often leads to overcrowding and negatively affects the quality of life of the local population.
Montenegro	Local resident	D3_ALL_ME	Yes	The development of cruise tourism in Boka Kotorska should be planned and regulated to ensure sustainability for future generations.
Montenegro	Local resident	D3_ALL_ME	Yes	Cruise tourism in Boka Kotorska often leads to overcrowding and negatively affects the quality of life of the local population.
Malta	Tourists and local visitors	D3_TL_MT	Yes	I would be willing to pay an eco-tax to contribute to the conservation of Comino.
Malta	Tourists and local visitors	D4_TL_MT	Yes	I would walk 15 minutes to visit an environmental education centre if there was one.
Malta	Commercial operators (tour / boat / beach services)	D3_CO_MT	Yes	I would support a visitor-paid eco-tax that would be used to pay for site management and conservation on Comino.
Malta	Commercial operators (tour / boat / beach services)	D4_CO_MT	Yes	I am willing to pass on information to visitors to help them understand how we can look after nature on Comino.
Malta	Relevant public authorities (environment and tourism ministries, tourism authority, local councils)	D3_PA_MT	Yes	I would support a visitor-paid eco-tax that would be used to pay for site management and conservation on Comino.
Malta	Relevant public authorities	D4_PA_MT	Yes	More holistic management and enforcement is needed for

	(environment and tourism ministries, tourism authority, local councils)			protecting the whole Natura 2000 site and the adjacent Marine Protected Areas (MPAs).
Slovenia	Farmers	D3_ALL_SI	Yes	I support increasing knowledge in data collection and species density in agricultural landscapes to improve the management of wildlife and invasive species.
Slovenia	Farmers	D4_ALL_SI	Yes	I regularly contribute to public awareness regarding biodiversity conservation and human-wildlife conflicts.
Slovenia	Local community	D3_ALL_SI	Yes	I support increasing knowledge in data collection and species density in agricultural landscapes to improve the management of wildlife and invasive species.
Slovenia	Local community	D4_ALL_SI	Yes	I regularly contribute to public awareness regarding biodiversity conservation and human-wildlife conflicts.
Slovenia	Protected area practitioners	D3_ALL_SI	Yes	I support increasing knowledge in data collection and species density in agricultural landscapes to improve the management of wildlife and invasive species.
Slovenia	Protected area practitioners	D4_ALL_SI	Yes	I regularly contribute to public awareness regarding biodiversity conservation and human-wildlife conflicts.
Romania	Local authorities	D3_ALL_RO	Yes	I would be willing to pay a small additional fee when visiting Corbu Beach if I knew the money would be used to protect it.
Romania	Local authorities	D4_ALL_RO	Yes	I consider Corbu Beach to be a wild beach with a special protected status, rather than a regular tourist beach.
Romania	NGO	D3_ALL_RO	Yes	I would be willing to pay a small additional fee when visiting Corbu Beach if I knew the money would be used to protect it.
Romania	NGO	D4_ALL_RO	Yes	I consider Corbu Beach to be a wild beach with a special protected status, rather than a regular tourist beach.
Romania	Tourist	D3_ALL_RO	Yes	I would be willing to pay a small additional fee when visiting Corbu

				Beach if I knew the money would be used to protect it.
Romania	Tourist	D4_ALL_RO	Yes	I consider Corbu Beach to be a wild beach with a special protected status, rather than a regular tourist beach.
Romania	Local business sector	D3_ALL_RO	Yes	I would be willing to pay a small additional fee when visiting Corbu Beach if I knew the money would be used to protect it.
Romania	Local business sector	D4_ALL_RO	Yes	I consider Corbu Beach to be a wild beach with a special protected status, rather than a regular tourist beach.
Romania	Resident of Corbu	D3_ALL_RO	Yes	I would be willing to pay a small additional fee when visiting Corbu Beach if I knew the money would be used to protect it.
Romania	Resident of Corbu	D4_ALL_RO	Yes	I consider Corbu Beach to be a wild beach with a special protected status, rather than a regular tourist beach.
Estonia	Local Residents / Coastal Community Members	D3_LC_EE	Yes	When visiting the Laulasmaa–Kloogaranna area, I follow conservation rules (e.g., parking only in designated areas and making campfires only in marked fire sites).
Estonia	Local Residents / Coastal Community Members	D4_LC_EE	Yes	If I observe prohibited activities (e.g., making a campfire in a restricted area, illegal parking, or illegal fishing), I am willing to report it to the relevant authority (via the national information number 1247).
Estonia	Municipal Officials / Public Authorities	D3_MO_EE	No	Effective enforcement and cooperation with the Environmental Board help reduce environmental violations (e.g., illegal parking, campfires, littering).
Estonia	Municipal Officials / Public Authorities	D4_MO_EE	Yes	Coastal planning in this area should carefully consider fire risk, conservation requirements, and visitor pressure.
Estonia	Tourism and Business Stakeholders	D3_TB_EE	Yes	As a business operator, I encourage visitors to follow the conservation rules in the Laulasmaa–Kloogaranna area (e.g., parking regulations, campfire rules, proper waste disposal).

Estonia	Tourism and Business Stakeholders	D4_TB_EE	Yes	I have downloaded the “RMK in harmony with nature” mobile application and recommend it to visitors to help them find designated camping and campfire sites and view protected area boundaries.
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